

DESIGN AND UPGRADE CONSTRUCTIONAL SAFETY EQUIPMENT BY USING AI TECHNOLOGY WITH CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK

Mr. Gaurav Vispute¹, Dr. Sandeep Choudhary², Dr. Nagendrakumar U Daharwal³, Mr. Ashish Waghmare⁴
^{1, 2, 3, 4} Department of Civil Engineering, IES University, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India.

Abstract

The construction industry is one of the leading industries in the world. Wearisome safety equipment on the construction site is a very important and necessary thing to do, whether construction activities are going on or not. Wearing a protection helmet is a must and should be worn by all the people who are present on site, especially the laborer. There are very serious and deadly consequences of neglecting safety rules and regulations, as coincidences like falling material, being pierced by sharp things, cuts, bruises, etc. happen unpredictably and result in severe injuries or even loss. Depending on the type and severity of accidents, they may cause temporary or permanent disability; in the worst-case situation, death is also possible. These accidents also impact the organization's cost and reputation as it must compensate injured workers or their families. After the accident, the organization has to face various types of criticism from people and workers. To minimize accidents on construction sites, the government has issued various laws and regulations that should be followed by employers and employees; they also require constant physical supervision to enforce safety, which makes things a little bit tedious. We need to implement enhanced supervision management to ensure that workers should at least wear safety helmets all the time. This reading should help make improvements to the traditional safety helmet while proposing a new enhanced monitoring management to ensure safety.

Keywords: Fates on Construction Site, Safety Management System, PPE Kit, Convolutional Neural Network

1. Introduction

Sung Hun Kim et.al had enhanced the study in the Korean construction industry. They infer that letdown to wear safety helmets seems to be one of the major causes of the increase in accidents, and so it is essential to develop technology to monitor whether or not safety helmets are being used. However, the approaches employed in existing technical studies on this issue have mainly involved the use of chinstrap sensors and have been limited to the problem of whether or not safety helmets are being worn. But it is observed that improper wearing, such as when the chinstrap and bind fixing of the safety helmet are not properly tightened, has not been monitored. To remedy this shortcoming, the authors have developed a safety helmet with a three-axis accelerometer sensor attached [1].

Yuwan Gu et. al described that that finding of safety helmets is difficult and low precise while worn in the complex pose of a construction worker. So to address this issue, a method for detecting safety helmet wear based on pose estimation was proposed. For that, they used the YOLO V4

technique to detect the safety helmet region. With this method's help, they designed the pose estimation model for an open pose. The residual network optimized feature extraction was introduced to obtain the skeletal point info of the construction worker, and then the pose of the worker was estimated based on the skeletal point information [2].

Wu Hao et. al observed that personal labor protection equipment and wearing a safety helmet appropriately can help prevent and control collision damage. But in actual operation, there are still some workers who are affected by the lack of comfort of a safety helmet, and they were not willing to wear a safety helmet. It is also surveyed about the factors that lead to discomfort from wearing a helmet. Also, 15% of injuries are caused by not wearing a safety helmet. On some level, the paper shows safety helmet comfort research, but we have not further studied the influencing factors of safety helmet comfort [3].

Johannes De Boer et. al had discussed that construction sites, workers are required to wear personal protective equipment during their work. But there is often a lack of motivation to wear them. The series of projects consist of raising intrinsic motivation to wear safety helmets by adding features and making the safety helmet more comfortable to wear. The first project got a clear view of the problems and why workers were having trouble while wearing safety helmets. Later projects focused on designing prototypes, constructing samples so that they could become more wearable and effective, and eventually conducting usability studies with construction site workers [4].

M. Saniya, Amulya et. al observed visually examine the site and understand the failure in wearing the safety helmet. A video tape monitoring system was used for real-time results. They also develop a deep learning-based system for the real-time monitoring of a safety helmet at the construction point by means of the YOLO algorithm, which also includes a module that is able to detect whether the worker is working or idle and also analyze the movement of the worker in real-time. They also suggest using colored safety helmets according to the employee profile. So that it will be easier to monitor safety helmet management [5]. According to experimental results, it was demonstrated that the presented deep learning-based model using the SSD-Mobile Net algorithm is capable of detecting the unsafe operation of not wearing a helmet at the construction site with satisfactory accuracy and efficiency [6]. In this paper upgraded safety helmets make improvements to the traditional safety helmet while proposing a new enhanced monitoring supervision to ensure safety.

2. Problem Identified

During the entire reading, various parameters were reflected, most influencing parameters were considered and mentioned below towards the conclusion of the said study.

- Due to various reasons labors incline to neglect wearing safety helmets irrespective of protocols.

- Lack of suitable administration for wearing safety helmet on construction site.
- It makes difficult for construction supervisor to constantly supervise and enforce to wear safety helmet physically on larger and multilevel construction site.

3. Data Collection:

PPE generally includes the following equipment:

1. Safety Helmet
2. Protective Cloths
3. Safety Gloves
4. Safety Spectacles
5. Hearing protection gearing
6. Foot protection gear
7. High Visibility Vest
8. Safety Harness.

- **Factors affecting on safety helmet wearing:**

We focused our study on the safety helmet from the PPE kit because it protects the most important part of the body, i.e., the head. An injury to the head may lead to temporary or permanent damage to the body, and a safety helmet proved to be a good way to minimize that. According to the study, a survey was conducted on 36 people about the discomfort or hesitation behind not wearing a safety helmet.

- **Factors for Not Wearing Safety Helmet:**

According to the study, a survey conducted on 36 people about discomfort or hesitation behind not wearing safety helmet. In that study it is observed following factors for not wearing safety helmets.

Graph No 1. Factors for not wearing Safety helmet

- 25% of people react that they have a problem in viewing, followed by 22% of people react that combined hotness, sweating, and itching are the significant problems for discomfort.

- 14% responded that they felt discomfort with the nape strap
- 11% of people react that they felt discomfort with the chin strap.
- 8% of people react that both sweating and itching were the problems
- 8% of people react that only itching was the major problem for their discomfort.
- 6% of people react that only sweating was the problem, and on another side
- 6% of the people respond that both nape strap and chin strap were major problems for their discomfort.

4. Methodology

This section describes the materials, equipment, and methods used in this technology.

Method Selection: As observed from the above research and study, to overcome such challenges we choose safety helmet specifically to enhance and working with; as it is absolutely necessary we propose to develop safety helmet wearing management where we develop a smart helmet using proximity sensor. This smart helmet consist of regular safety helmet used on construction site along with the electronics components like controller, proximity PIR sensor , boost converter, sim card, battery and charger which we are going to study in details further.

Flow Chart of Smart Helmet Design:

Fig No 1. Assembly of smart helmet

- It work on a principle where human body constantly emits thermal radiation from within via skin which we can be sensed by infrared thermometer. This sensor is situated at the inner side of the helmet on the top of the head. Sensor then further connected with the STM controller where it takes input from the sensor and will send command to GSM900.
- STM controller then initiate the sequence to send message to the supervisor's device and GSM900 will transmit the actual message to the device. To send message from GSM900 module, it must contain a SIM card within it. Controller can also receive the input command like text of the message if necessary.

- **List of Components:**

Sr. No	Component
1	Safety Helmet
2	HC-SR501 PIR Proximity Sensor
3	STM32F103 Controller
4	Lithium Battery
5	Micro USB 5V 1A 18650 Charger
6	GSM900a Module
7	Wires

Table No. 2 List of Components

- **Components of Smart Helmet:**

Safety Helmet:

Fig No 3. Safety helmet used in construction industry

- Safety helmets are a type of headgear which are worn by workers who are engaged in industrial or construction sites in order to protect the head from injuries which are caused by falling objects, debris, rain, electric shock etc.

Design of the Safety Helmet:

1. Shell should be dome shaped, no metallic components are to be used. Brim diameter should be 6mm, peak 50mm. Diameter of the hole for ventilation should not exceed 6mm and maintained at a distance not less than 15mm from adjacent hole. Number of holes should be more than 3 but the average area of all holes should not exceed 300mm
2. The headband should be more than 30mm in width. Cradle should be secured at minimum of four anchoring points. Straps should be anti-concussion and width not less than 19 mm. Straps should be fitted such that minimum clearance be at least 30 mm and maximum clearance more than 80 mm.

3. Chin strap should have minimum width of 19 mm and directly attached to shell. Nape strip should have minimum depth of 115 mm.
4. The mass of helmet without attachments should be 400 g. If it is to exceed 400 g, with nearing 35 g, it should be labelled.

HC-SR501 PIR Proximity Sensor:**Fig No 4. PIR Sensor**

The PIR (Passive Infrared Radiation) sensor allows us to detect when a person or animal moves in or out of sensor range. It is almost always used to detect the motion of a human body within the sensors range. It is often referred to using “PIR”, “Pyroelectric”, “Passive infrared” and “IR MOTION” sensor.

A PIR sensor consists of two main parts:

Pyroelectric Sensor:**Fig No.5 Pyroelectric Sensor**

A pyroelectric sensor consists of a window with two rectangular slots and is made of a material that allows infrared radiation to pass through. Behind the window, there are two separate infrared sensor electrodes, one responsible for producing the positive output and the other for producing the negative output. The two electrodes are wired such that they cancel each other out.

Fresnel lens:**Fig No.6 Fresnel lens**

This lens is used to focus the infrared signals on the pyroelectric sensor. This lens consists of a series of concentric grooves carved into the plastic. These contours act as individual refracting surfaces, gathering parallel light rays at a focal point. As a result a Fresnel lens, although smaller in size, is able to focus light similarly to a conventional optical lens.

Hardware Specifications of HC-SR501 PIR Proximity Sensor:

Operating Voltage	3.3 V to 20V
Maximum Current Draw	< 2mA
Time Delay	1 sec to 3 min
Detection Distance	3 to 7 meters (9 to 21 feet)
Detection Angle	120 degrees

Table No 3. Specifications of HC-SR501 PIR Proximity Sensor

Working:

In summary, this PIR sensor's working is very straightforward and simple. When simply apply power via battery 3.3V to 20V, the sensor output goes HIGH when motion is detected and goes LOW when no motion detected. We can connect this output to the microcontroller so that we can configure the controller to get desired output in the text format.

STM32F103 Controller:

Fig No.7 Controller

STM32F103 microcontrollers is one of the important component in smart helmet assembly. It connected to the PIR proximity sensor. STM32F103 microcontrollers can be used to convert Analog signals to Digital signal with the ADC (Analog to Digital Converter) embedded within it. Any information may be carried by an Analog signal; such a signal may be a measured response to changes in a physical variable, such as sound, light, temperature, position or pressure. A digital signal is a signal that represents data as a sequence of discrete values. This contrasts with an Analog signal, which represents continuous values; at any given time it represents a real number within a continuous range of values.

Lithium battery:

Fig No.8 Lithium Battery

This smart helmet uses battery which connected to the STM controller and GSM900a module for power supply and can be charged by using Micro USB 5V 1A 18650 charger. The cells are connected in parallel and spot-welded to a protection circuit that provides over-voltage, under-voltage, and over-current protection. **Micro USB 5V 1A 18650 Charger:**

Fig No.9 Micro USB Charger

Fig No.10 Overview of charger and battery assembly

Micro USB 5V 1A 18650 charger is a complete single lithium-ion battery with a constant current / constant-voltage linear charger. Bottom finned ESOP8 with DIP8 Package, with low external component count of such TC4056A ideal for portable applications like Bluetooth speakers, portable chargers etc. It contain micro USB slot so that micro USB cable can able charge the connected battery within helmet.

Working and Configuration of Components of Smart Helmet:

We can connect PIR output to any digital pin. There is a jumper behind this module. If we move the jumper to L position, the sensor will ‘toggle’ (change state) whenever motion is detected. This is unlikely to be of much use in a practical applications. This mode is called non-triggering or

single triggering mode. Moving the jumper to the H position will result in the more usual sensor logic. The sensor will turn on when motion is detected and turn off a while after the last motion is detected. This sensor will reset the timer (which would otherwise turn the output off) each time motion is detected. This is called Retriggering mode or repeatable trigger mode. There are also two potentiometers behind this module. By changing the sensitivity potentiometer, you can reduce or increase the sensitivity of the sensor (clockwise increase), and also by changing potentiometer the output delay after movement detection will be changed.

A configuration of the controller is done in Arduino IDE where first, we need to install Arduino IDE then we have to select the controller in the “ Select Board “ drop and as we can see in fig () we select STM32Fxxxx series controller for configuration and then a simple code is deployed in IDE.

5. Recommendation

Researching, reviewing literature and studying case studies, we obtained the following recommendation:

Workers were not wearing PPE, which resulted in on-site accidents like falling objects and impacts to the head. These accidents can be minimized by wearing personal protective equipment, especially safety helmets.

6. Conclusion

This paper reveals the in-depth study in the main findings of this work, outlines the contributions and limitations of this research and identifies future research are as follows:

1. The construction industry is dangerous and following safety regulations is important for both employees and employers.
2. Wearing PPE kit is a must, especially safety helmets, all the time whenever present on site. Most of the injuries happened on site; more than 70% are due to not wearing a safety helmet.
3. Workers tend to feel uncomfortable wearing safety helmets due to various reasons but irrespective of that, for the greater good and to ensure safety, there should be strict supervision from the employers.

References

1. Sung Hun Kim, Changwon Wang, Se Dong Min and Seung Hyun Lee, “Safety Helmet Wearing Management System for Construction Workers Using Three-Axis Accelerometer Sensor.” November 2018.
2. Yuwan Gu, Yusheng Wang, Lin Shi, Ning Li, Lihua Zhuang, Shoukun Xu, “ Automatic detection of safety helmet wearing based on head region location.” March 2021.
3. Wu Hao, Luo Shan, Wang Yang, Wang Jingjing, Li Chenyan, Zou Yun, “ Analysis of the Influence Factors of Safety Helmet Comfort ”. Anhui Xinhua University, Hefei, Anhui, 230088, China, 2019.

4. Johannes de boer, margot stilma , karin van beurden and wouter teeuw, “ a series of student design projects for improving and modernizing safety helmets “international conference on engineering and product design education.”, university of twente, the Netherlands. September 2014
5. M. Saniya, Amulya, A. Sahiti, B. A. Nagarani, Dr. M. Shanker, “Construction Site Accident Avoidance”. ISSN: 2321-9653; IC Value: 45.98; SJ Impact Factor: 7.538 Volume 10, Issue VI, June 2022.
6. Yange Li, Han Wei, Zheng Han, Jianling Huang and Weidong Wang “Deep Learning- Based Safety Helmet Detection in Engineering Management Based on Convolutional Neural Networks.” September 2020.
7. Israel Campero-Jurado, Sergio Márquez-Sánchez, Juan Quintanar-Góme, Sara Rodríguez and Juan M. Corchado. “Smart Helmet 5.0 for Industrial Internet of Things Using Artificial Intelligence “.1 November 2020.
8. Dilip A Patel, Kumar Neeraj Jha. “An Estimate of Fatal Accidents in Indian Construction “. July 2016
9. Vigneshkumar Chellappa, Urmi Salve. “Why Does an Indian Construction Worker Fail to Wear Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) at Workplace?” June 2022.
10. Michael Bottlang, Gina DiGiacomo, Stanley Tsai, and Steven Madey. “Effect of helmet design on impact performance of industrial safety helmets” Biomechanics Laboratory, Legacy Research Institute, Portland, OR, 97232, USA, July 2022.
11. Zhe Hu1, Weng Tat Chan, “Cognitive Factors Underlying Unsafe Behaviors of Construction Workers as a Tool in Safety Management: A Review” American Society of Civil Engineers, june2023
12. Hoonyong Lee1, et-al “Collective Sensing of Workers’ Loss of Body Balance for Slip, Trip, and Fall Hazard Identification: Field Validation Study”, American Society of Civil Engineers, 2023
13. Donghai Liu et.al , “Integrating Building Information Model and Augmented Reality for Drone-Based Building Inspection, American Society of Civil Engineers, 2021
14. Asif Mansoor et.al, “A Deep-Learning Classification Framework for Reducing Communication Errors in Dynamic Hand Signaling for Crane Operation, American Society of Civil Engineers, 2023
15. Hector Martin et.al. “Exploring the Role of PPE Knowledge, Attitude, and Correct Practices in Safety Outcomes on Construction Sites” American Society of Civil Engineers, 2021

16. Manu Akula et.al. “ Context-Aware Framework for Highway Bridge Inspections”, American Society of Civil Engineers, 2015
17. Cenfei Sun et.al. “ Identifying Workers’ Safety Behavior–Related Personality by Sensing” 2020
18. Heidi Wagner et.al. “Relationship between Personal Protective Equipment, Self-Efficacy, and Job Satisfaction of Women in the Building Trades” American Society of Civil Engineers, 2013
19. Hua-Ping Wan et. al. “Improved Vision-Based Method for Detection of Unauthorized Intrusion by Construction Sites Workers”, American Society of Civil Engineers, 2023
20. Xuetong Wang et al. “Development of an Internet-of-Things-Based Technology System for Construction Safety Hazard Prevention, American Society of Civil Engineers, 2022
21. Han Wu et.al. “Identifying Unsafe Behavior of Construction Workers: A Dynamic Approach Combining Skeleton Information and Spatiotemporal Features” American Society of Civil Engineers, 2023
22. Chang Jae Yeol et. al., “Quantifying the Effectiveness of IoT Technologies for Accident Prevention”, American Society of Civil Engineers, 2020
23. Peichen Zhai1, et. al. , “ Extracting Worker Unsafe Behaviors from Construction Images Using Image Captioning with Deep Learning–Based Attention Mechanism”, American Society of Civil Engineers, 2023
24. Hong Zhang et.al. “Real-Time Alarming, Monitoring, and Locating for Non-Hard-Hat Use in Construction”, American Society of Civil Engineers, 2019